

**A CLINICAL EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF CHATURJATAK CHURNA
PRADHAMANA NASYA AND SHATHYADI CHURNA ABHYANTARPANA IN
PRATISHYAYA****¹Dr. Rekha G. Pandey, ²Dr. Priti V. Gahukar, ³Dr. Vedprakash D. Gahukar**¹HOD & Professor, Department of Samhita Siddhant Smt. Shantibai Otarmal Jain Ayurvedic Rugnalaya, Raigad(MH).²Associate Professor, Department of Samhita Siddhant Indutai Gaikwad Patil Ayurvedic College, Nagpur (MH).³Ayurveda Head, Med Ayu Hospital, Nagpur.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Rekha G. Pandey**HOD & Professor, Department of Samhita Siddhant Smt. Shantibai Otarmal Jain Ayurvedic Rugnalaya, Raigad(MH). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18151655>**How to cite this Article:** ¹Dr. Rekha G. Pandey, ²Dr. Priti V. Gahukar, ³Dr. Vedprakash D. Gahukar. (2026). A Clinical Evaluation Of The Effect Of Chaturjatak Churna Pradhamana Nasya And Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana In Pratishyaya. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(1), 531-536.

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ABSTRACT

Pratishyaya is a commonly encountered nasal disorder described in Ayurvedic literature under the group of *Nasagata Vikaras*. It is characterized by symptoms such as nasal discharge, nasal obstruction, sneezing, headache, heaviness of the head, and inflammation of the nasal mucosa. Since the classical period of Ayurveda, Pratishyaya has been recognized as a disease with multifactorial etiology and complex pathophysiology. From a modern perspective, it closely resembles allergic rhinitis, which is an IgE-mediated hypersensitivity disorder affecting the nasal airway mucosa.^[1,5] Ayurvedic texts emphasize *Nasya Karma* as the principal line of treatment for disorders of the nose and head region, as the nose is considered the gateway to *Shiras*.^[2,3] Among various forms of Nasya, *Pradhamana Nasya* is regarded as the most effective *Shodhana* procedure for eliminating accumulated Doshas in Pratishyaya.^[4] Yogaratnakara specifically mentions *Chaturjatak Churna Pradhamana Nasya* along with *Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana* administered with Guda and Ghrita for the management of all types of Pratishyaya.^[7-9] The present study aims to evaluate the combined and individual effects of Chaturjatak Churna Nasya and Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana in the management of Pratishyaya. The study also attempts to understand the Ayurvedic rationale and probable mode of action of these formulations in alleviating the symptoms and breaking the pathogenesis of the disease.

KEYWORDS: Pratishyaya, Pradhamana Nasya, Chaturjatak Churna, Shathyadi Churna, Allergic Rhinitis.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda describes Panchakarma as a specialized branch of treatment that aims at eliminating vitiated Doshas from the body and restoring them to their normal sites. The manifestation of disease begins when Doshas move from *Koshtha* to *Shakha*, and Panchakarma therapies are designed to bring these Doshas back to Koshtha for elimination.^[1] Among Panchakarma procedures, Nasya holds a unique position in the management of diseases affecting the organs above the clavicle (*Urdhvajatrugata Roga*).^[2]

The head (*Shiras*) is considered *Uttamanga*, as it is the seat of all sensory and motor functions and the controller of the entire body. The nose (*Nasa*) is not only an organ

of respiration but also serves as an important route for the administration of medicines directly to the head region.^[3] Nasya Karma utilizes this route to deliver drugs that act locally as well as systemically by clearing obstructed channels and pacifying vitiated Doshas.

Pratishyaya is one of the most important Nasagata Vikaras described in Ayurvedic texts. It is considered an acute disorder of *Pranavaha Srotas* and is also mentioned as a *Purvarupa* of Rajayakshma.^[4] Classical texts describe that only Charaka and Kashyapa have elaborated the general symptoms of Pratishyaya. The disease is characterized by excessive nasal discharge, sneezing, nasal obstruction, headache, heaviness in the head, and altered smell sensation.^[2,4]

From a contemporary medical viewpoint, Pratishtyaya can be correlated with allergic rhinitis, which is an IgE-mediated hypersensitivity disorder of the nasal mucosa. It significantly affects the quality of life and is associated with symptoms such as rhinorrhea, nasal congestion, itching, sneezing, and headache.^[1,5] Chronic or untreated Pratishtyaya may progress to *Dushtapratishyaya*, which closely resembles chronic rhinosinusitis described in modern medicine.^[6]

Ayurvedic classics clearly state that the main line of treatment for Pratishtyaya is *Shodhana Nasya*, as the disease involves accumulation of Kapha and other Doshas in the nasal passages. Among all types of *Shodhana Nasya*, *Pradhamana Nasya* is considered the most effective in expelling vitiated Doshas from the nasal cavity.^[4,7]

Yogarajnakara specifically advocates the use of *Chaturjatak Churna* for *Pradhamana Nasya* in Pratishtyaya and recommends *Shathyadi Churna* with *Guda* and *Ghritha* for internal administration. These formulations are described as possessing *Doshaghna*, *Shothahara*, *Strotoshodhana*, and *Rasayana* properties, which help in breaking the pathogenesis of Pratishtyaya and preventing recurrence.^[7-9]

AIM

To evaluate the effect of **Chaturjatak Churna Pradhamana Nasya** and **Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana** in the management of Pratishtyaya.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the Ayurvedic concept of Pratishtyaya.
2. To study the concept and clinical features of *Dushtapratishyaya*.
3. To study the composition and properties of *Chaturjatak Churna* and *Shathyadi Churna*.
4. To understand the mode of action of *Chaturjatak Churna Nasya* and *Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana*.
5. To evaluate the efficacy of *Shathyadi Churna* in the management of *Vataja Pratishtyaya*.
6. To assess the role of *Chaturjatak Pradhamana Nasya* in the treatment of *Dushtapratishyaya*.

CONCEPT OF PRATISHYAYA (AYURVEDIC VIEW)

Pratishtyaya is described in Ayurvedic literature as a *Nasagata Vikara* caused by the vitiation of Doshas, predominantly Kapha and Vata. The disease manifests when vitiated Doshas accumulate in the nasal passages, leading to obstruction of channels and excessive secretions.^[2,4] Improper diet, exposure to cold, dust, smoke, allergens, and suppression of natural urges are considered important etiological factors.

According to Charaka, Pratishtyaya is an acute disorder of *Pranavaha Srotas* and may present as a *Purvarupa* of *Rajyakshma*.^[4] The involvement of Kapha Dosha is

prominent in the chronic stage, known as *Dushtapratishyaya*, which is considered a complication of repeated or improperly treated Pratishtyaya rather than a separate disease entity.^[6]

Sushruta has described nasal disorders under *Urdhvajatrugata Rogas* and emphasized the importance of eliminating accumulated Doshas through appropriate *Shodhana* therapies, particularly *Nasya*.^[2,3] In *Dushtapratishyaya*, symptoms such as purulent nasal discharge, headache, heaviness of head, facial pain, nasal obstruction, and anosmia are commonly observed, closely resembling chronic rhinosinusitis.^[6]

From a modern perspective, Pratishtyaya can be correlated with allergic rhinitis, which involves IgE-mediated inflammation of the nasal mucosa. Studies have shown that allergic rhinitis significantly impairs quality of life and requires long-term management strategies.^[1,5]

RATIONALE FOR NASYA AND ABHYANTARA CHIKITSA

Ayurvedic texts emphasize that *Nasya* is the most appropriate therapy for diseases of the nose, head, and sensory organs. *Pradhamana Nasya* is especially indicated in conditions where Kapha Dosha is predominant, as it effectively expels Doshas from the nasal cavity.^[4,7]

Chaturjatak Churna possesses *Katu Rasa*, *Ushna Veerya*, *Tikshna* and *Sukshma Guna*, enabling it to penetrate minute channels and perform *Strotoshodhana*. The drug facilitates drainage of nasal secretions, reduces inflammation, and enhances local immunity.^[7-9]

Shathyadi Churna, when administered internally with *Guda* and *Ghritha*, acts as *Deepana*, *Pachana*, *Shothahara*, *Abhishyandahara*, and *Rasayana*. It also exhibits anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immunomodulatory, and anti-asthmatic properties, thereby reducing hypersensitivity reactions and preventing recurrence.^[8-10]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present clinical study was designed to evaluate the effect of **Chaturjatak Churna Pradhamana Nasya** and **Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana** in patients suffering from Pratishtyaya. The study was conducted at **Shrimati Shantibai Otarmal Jain Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital** in Velshet, Raigad, Maharashtra after a detailed understanding of the Ayurvedic concept of the disease and the therapeutic principles described in classical texts.^[2,4]

SELECTION OF PATIENTS

A total of **60 patients** diagnosed with Pratishtyaya were selected for the study. Patients were screened on the basis of classical signs and symptoms of Pratishtyaya and were examined clinically. A detailed case record form

was maintained for each patient to document demographic data, clinical findings, and treatment response.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Patients diagnosed with Pratishtyaya
- Age group between **10 and 80 years**
- Patients irrespective of sex, religion, and socio-economic status
- Patients presenting with features comparable to rhinitis

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Patients suffering from **Diabetes Mellitus**
- Patients suffering from **Hypertension**
- **Pregnant women**
- Patients below **10 years** and above **80 years** of age

STUDY DESIGN AND GROUPING

The selected 60 patients were divided into **two main age-based groups**, and each group was further subdivided into three subgroups.

Group A – Young Age Group (14–40 years)

- **A1:** Treated with Chaturjatak Churna Pradhamana Nasya (10 patients)
- **A2:** Treated with Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana (10 patients)
- **A3:** Treated with combined Chaturjatak Churna Nasya and Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana (10 patients)

Group B – Senile Age Group (40–80 years)

- **B1:** Treated with Chaturjatak Churna Pradhamana Nasya (10 patients)
- **B2:** Treated with Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana (10 patients)
- **B3:** Treated with combined Chaturjatak Churna Nasya and Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana (10 patients)

This grouping enabled assessment of individual and combined effects of both therapies across different age groups.

INTERVENTION AND POSOLOGY

Chaturjatak Churna Pradhamana Nasya

- **Dose:** 125 mg (3 Muchunti)
- **Time of administration:** Early morning and before sunset
- **Duration:** 8 days
- **Type:** Pradhamana Nasya

Pradhamana Nasya was selected as it is the most effective Shodhana Nasya for expelling Kapha-predominant Doshas from the nasal cavity.^[4,7]

Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana

- **Dose:** 3 grams, twice daily
- **Duration:** 8 days
- **Anupana:** Guda and Ghrita

Internal administration was advised to correct Agni, pacify Doshas systemically, and prevent recurrence of symptoms.^[8-10]

DURATION OF STUDY

Each patient was treated for **8 days**. Clinical assessment was carried out on.

- Day 0 (before treatment)
- Day 2
- Day 4
- Day 6
- Day 8 (after completion of treatment)

These intervals were selected to assess the progressive response of therapy.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Assessment was based on **subjective and objective parameters**. Symptoms were graded based on severity and improvement.

Subjective Parameters

- Nasal discharge (Rhinorrhea)
- Nasal obstruction
- Sneezing
- Headache
- Heaviness in the head

Objective Parameters

- Rhinoscopic findings
- Nasal mucosal congestion
- Nasagata Sleshmala Kala Shotha

GRADATION OF SYMPTOMS

Each symptom was graded as follows.

- **0** – Absent
- **+** – Mild
- **++** – Moderate
- **+++** – Severe

OBSERVATIONS

Out of 60 registered patients, the majority completed the study. A few dropouts were observed in the senile age group treated with Shathyadi Churna alone and combined therapy. Overall compliance was satisfactory, and no serious adverse effects were reported during the treatment period.

Demographic Observations

- In the **young age group**, maximum patients were between **20–30 years**.
- In the **senile age group**, maximum patients were between **60–70 years**.
- The disease was observed in both genders, indicating **no gender specificity**.
- Occupational exposure to dust, cold air, and irritants was commonly noted, supporting the role of environmental factors in Pratishtyaya.^[11,6]

RESULTS

Effect on Rhinorrhea

All treatment groups showed improvement in rhinorrhea. However, the **combined therapy group** demonstrated greater percentage improvement compared to Nasya or Abhyantarpana alone. This suggests a synergistic effect of local Shodhana and systemic Dosha pacification.^[7-9]

Effect on Headache

Significant reduction in headache was observed in all groups by the 8th day. Combined therapy showed slightly better results, indicating effective clearance of Doshas from Urdhvajatrugata Srotas.^[4,6]

Effect on Sneezing

Patients treated with Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana showed marked improvement in sneezing, possibly due to its anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory actions.^[8-10]

Effect on Nasal Obstruction

Nasal obstruction improved significantly in all groups. Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana and combined therapy showed better relief, indicating effective Abhishyandahara and Srotoshodhana properties.^[8-11]

Effect on Nasagata Sleshmala Kala Shotha

Reduction in nasal mucosal inflammation was observed in both age groups, with better improvement noted in the senile age group. This indicates the effectiveness of Nasya and Abhyantarpana even in chronic conditions.^[6,7]

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis was carried out using:

- Wilcoxon Z test
- Mann-Whitney U test

The analysis revealed **no statistically significant difference** between the effects of Chaturjatak Churna Nasya and Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana when used individually. However, clinically, combined therapy showed superior results in symptom relief.^[13-15]

DISCUSSION

Pratishyaya is a multifactorial disease described in Ayurveda under Nasagata Vikaras, involving Dosha vitiation with predominant Kapha association and Vata involvement in later stages. Classical texts recognize Pratishyaya as an acute disorder of Pranavaha Srotas and also describe its occurrence as a Purvarupa of Rajayakshma.^[2,4] From a contemporary perspective, the disease closely resembles allergic rhinitis, which is an IgE-mediated hypersensitivity reaction of the nasal mucosa, significantly affecting quality of life.^[1,5]

The present study was undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of Chaturjatak Churna Pradhamana Nasya and Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana, individually and in combination, in the management of Pratishyaya. The selection of Pradhamana Nasya was based on classical references stating that it is the most effective form of Shodhana Nasya for eliminating accumulated Kapha Dosha from the nasal cavity.^[4,7] Internal administration of Shathyadi Churna with Guda and Ghrita was advised to correct Agni, pacify systemic Dosha imbalance, and prevent recurrence.^[8-10]

Discussion on Demographic Data

In the present study, Pratishyaya was observed in both young and senile age groups, indicating that the disease is not age-specific. Maximum patients in the young age group were between 20–30 years, while in the senile age group, most patients belonged to the 60–70 years age bracket. This distribution suggests that environmental exposure, lifestyle factors, and reduced immunity in elderly individuals may contribute to disease manifestation.^[1,6]

Gender-wise distribution showed that Pratishyaya affected both males and females, with no significant gender predisposition. This observation supports the Ayurvedic view that Dosha vitiation rather than gender determines disease occurrence.^[2,4]

Occupational history revealed that many patients were exposed to dust, cold air, and irritants, or had habits such as consumption of cold beverages after exertion. These factors are well-known Nidanās for Pratiśhyaya described in Ayurvedic literature and are also recognized as triggers for allergic rhinitis in modern medicine.^[1,5,6]

Discussion on Therapeutic Response

The results of the study demonstrated improvement in all major symptoms of Pratiśhyaya, including rhinorrhea, headache, sneezing, nasal obstruction, and Nasagata Sleshmala Kala Shotha.

- **Rhinorrhea:** All treatment groups showed improvement, but the combined therapy group exhibited greater percentage relief. This can be attributed to the synergistic action of Nasya, which clears local Doshā accumulation, and Abhyantarpana, which corrects systemic Doshā imbalance.^[7-9]
- **Headache:** Reduction in headache was observed across all groups, suggesting effective clearance of Urdhvajatrugata Doshās. The relief was more pronounced with combined therapy, indicating enhanced Srotoshodhana and Shothahara effects.^[4,6]
- **Sneezing:** Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana showed better control of sneezing, possibly due to its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties, which reduce hypersensitivity reactions.^[8-10]
- **Nasal Obstruction:** Significant improvement in nasal blockage was observed, particularly with Shathyadi Churna and combined therapy. The Abhishyandahara and Kaphashodhana actions of the drugs play a key role in relieving obstruction.^[8-11]
- **Nasagata Sleshmala Kala Shotha:** Reduction in nasal mucosal inflammation was evident in both age groups, with slightly better improvement in the senile age group. This suggests that Nasya and Abhyantarpana are effective even in chronic or recurrent cases.^[6,7]

Discussion on Mode of Action

Chaturjatak Churna predominantly possesses Katu and Tikta Rasa, Ushna Veerya, Laghu, Tikshna, and Sukshma Guna. These properties facilitate penetration into minute channels, perform Srotoshodhana, expel vitiated Kapha, and promote drainage of nasal secretions.^[7-9] The drug also exhibits Balya, Brimhana, and Rasayana effects by nourishing Dhatus and enhancing immunity, thereby reducing inflammation in the nasal cavity and sinuses.

Shathyadi Churna, when administered internally, acts as Deepana, Pachana, Shothahara, Abhishyandahara, and Rasayana. Modern studies cited in the reference literature also support its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immunomodulatory, mast-cell stabilizing, and anti-asthmatic properties, which justify its efficacy in allergic rhinitis and Pratiśhyaya.^[1,5,8,10]

Statistical Interpretation

Statistical analysis using Wilcoxon Z test and Mann–Whitney U test revealed that there was no statistically significant difference between the effects of Chaturjatak Churna Nasya and Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana when used individually. However, clinically, combined therapy showed better symptomatic relief, suggesting a complementary action of local and systemic treatment modalities.^[13-15]

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that Pratiśhyaya can be effectively managed with Chaturjatak Churna Pradhama Nasya and Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana. Both therapies were found to be individually effective in reducing the symptoms of Pratiśhyaya, while their combined use produced better clinical outcomes. No adverse effects were observed during the course of treatment, indicating that the therapies are safe, cost-effective, and well tolerated.

Pratiśhyaya can be correlated with allergic rhinitis, and the Ayurvedic management approach using Nasya and Abhyantarpana offers a holistic and effective alternative to conventional treatment. Thus, Chaturjatak Churna Nasya and Shathyadi Churna Abhyantarpana can be considered drugs of choice in the management of Pratiśhyaya.

SUMMARY

Pratiśhyaya is a complex disease with diverse symptoms and multifactorial pathogenesis. It has been described in Ayurvedic literature since the classical period. The disease involves Pranavaha Srotas and is associated with Kapha-Vata Doshā vitiation. Nasya is the main line of treatment for Pratiśhyaya. Pradhama Nasya is the most effective Shodhana Nasya. Chaturjatak Churna is beneficial in Pratiśhyaya when used as Nasya. Shathyadi Churna is effective as an internal medicine. Combined therapy shows superior results compared to individual treatment. The drugs are safe, cost-effective, and easy to administer.

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